

Applications of High Resolution Infrared Diode Laser Spectroscopy[†]

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Tunable diode lasers for the infrared region are now available commercially and can be used for general high resolution spectroscopic studies as well as in special techniques, like study of supercooled molecular beams, trace and ultratrace analysis, precise frequency and intensity measurements *etc.* The present paper reviews the techniques and applications of TDL-s in some of these fields, with special reference to molecules like ammonia, sulfur hexafluoride and heavy water.

HIGH resolution infrared spectra of polyatomic molecules in the free state give information on vibration-rotation energy levels, molecular geometry, molecular force fields, dipole moments, vibration-rotation interaction, intermolecular potentials *etc.* Such studies have become of great importance recently because of the advances in theory of vibration-rotation interaction in terms of molecular structure and symmetry and also because of the availability of narrow line width (10^{-4} cm^{-1}) tunable diode lasers spanning the entire infrared region of 3-30 μm , which enable very fine interactions to be determined accurately. Recent high resolution diode laser studies on molecules like SF_6 ¹, isotopic ammonias^{2,3} and substituted methanes⁴⁻⁷, to take only a few examples, illustrate the insight one can get on the complex interactions present in seemingly simple molecules. The theoretical analysis of the spectra thus gives a clear understanding of the finer details of quantum mechanical interpretation of molecular structure.

The understanding of many chemical physics problems depend on the detection and characterisation of one or more molecular species, before, during, and after collision processes involving photons, electrons, atoms, or molecules. The initial state parameters will strongly influence the relevant cross section of interest. The evolution of the reaction will be reflected on the process of the microscopic conversion of the translational and internal states of the reactants into the translational and internal states of the products, through the states of the intermediate complexes. The decay processes after the collision determine the final products. High resolution diode laser infrared spectroscopy can provide unambiguous information on most of the steps considered above. Very often these studies are carried out under molecular beam⁸⁻¹⁰ conditions, where the diode laser technique provides a very sensitive, non-destructive, non-perturbing probe¹¹⁻¹⁴.

A semiconductor diode laser spectrometer has been operational in our laboratory for the last few years. We have used this for several high resolution spectral studies, supercooled nozzle beam studies and applications in trace analysis^{9,7,14-17}. The present paper reviews some of our results and also summarises some of the important results from other laboratories. For more information on applications of diode laser spectroscopy, the reader may refer to some of the excellent review articles available in literature¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Experimental

The spectrometer in our laboratory is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The tunable diode lasers (TDL) are mounted on a closed cycle refrigerator cold head. A maximum of four lasers can be mounted on a single cold head so that a sufficiently large spectral region can be covered in any experiment, by applying current to any one of the four

Fig. 1. Tunable diode laser (TDL) spectrometer, schematic.

lasers and positioning its output into the sample cell, using a collimating lens, mounted on a precision XYZ translational stage. The beam from the cell is then focussed at the entrance slit to a 1/2 m grating monochromator, where it can be chopped

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Fig. 2. TDL spectrum of a section of the ν_{14} band of *s*-tetrazine. OCS lines used for reference can be seen in the spectrum. Dotted curve shows interference fringes from the 7.5 cm Ge-etalon, used for calibration.

by a tuning fork chopper. The monochromator is used to select a single mode of the laser, since usually the TDL gives its output in two or three different modes, separated by $2\text{--}3\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The radiation from the exit slit of the monochromator, is focussed on to a liquid N_2 cooled HgCdTe (MCT) detector. The signal from the detector is fed to a pre-amplifier and lock-in amplifier and used for recording the spectrum. Accurate calibration of the spectrum can be done by using a standard reference sample and fringes from a $3''$ Ge-etalon. A typical spectrum is shown in Fig. 2.

For supercooled nozzle beam experiments, the beam from the exit slit of the monochromator is recollimated and transported to the nozzle beam set up, a schematic of which is shown in Fig. 3. The TDL beam is then refocussed at the nozzle, its exact position along the molecular beam being precisely controlled by proper positioning of the focussing lens. After passing through the supercooled beam, the radiation is focussed on to the MCT detector by another lens, and spectrum recorded as before. For many spectral studies at low pressures and temperatures, and for trace analysis, we have used several types of long-path cells. In such experiments, the sample cells are kept outside the instrument, and the collimated laser beam transported along the required path and then returned to the monochromator entrance slit.

Results and Discussion

Molecular spectroscopy: As mentioned in the introduction, in this review we will illustrate some typical results of high resolution spectral studies which have given information on complex

interactions as evinced from finer details of the spectrum.

Fig. 3. Schematic of nozzle beam experimental set-up.

The ammonia molecule has always served as a good theoretical model for all vibration-rotation spectroscopy. It is well known that this molecule, in addition to its small amplitude vibrational

modes Q_1 , Q_3 and Q_4 possesses the large amplitude inversion motion Q_2 , which takes the place of the symmetric bending mode. This large amplitude motion is represented by the well known double minimum potential. Interaction between the small and large amplitude motions in this molecule gives rise to peculiar effects in the spectrum, some of which we have been able to observe in our high resolution studies. Similarly, deviations from the standard polynomial form of the energy levels of a symmetric rotor arising from perturbations due to $\Delta k = \pm 3n$ type interactions have also been observed in the isotopic ammonias. Such perturbations arise from near coincidences of symmetric and antisymmetric levels differing in K by 3 and the deviation observed from energy level calculation based on the polynomial expression give an idea of such interaction.

For the isotopic molecules $^{14}\text{NH}_3$ and $^{15}\text{NH}_3$, we have fitted more than 500 lines in the TDL spectrum of the ν_2 band (inversion mode), with an accuracy better than 0.0005 cm^{-1} (Ref. 3). In this fit, we started with the standard polynomial expression for the energy levels given by

$$E^0(J,K) = T_v + BJ(J+1) + (C-B)K^2 - \sum_{l=1} \sum_{m=0} (-1)^l D_{lm} J(J+1)^m K^{l-m}$$

where l is the order of the term and m the power of $J(J+1)$. (For comparison with conventional energy expression²¹ the quartic distortion constants D_J , D_{JK} and D_K are denoted by D_{33} , D_{31} and D_{30}). The $\Delta k = \pm 3n$ interactions modify this, and in the Nielsen-Dennison approximation²², the corrected energy levels are given by

$$E'(J,3) = E^0(J,3) \mp (-1)^J f(J,3)\eta_3$$

$$E'(J,6) = E^0(J,6) \pm (-1)^J f(J,3) \times f(J,6)\eta_6$$

where

$$f(J,K) = [J(J+1) - K(K-1)] [J(J+1) - (K-1)(K-2)] [J(J+1) - (K-2)(K-3)]$$

and η_3 and η_6 are constants.

Belov *et al.*²³ have shown that higher order interaction terms have to be incorporated for the ν_2 state and have given appropriate interaction matrix, with the diagonal elements as given above ($E^0(J,K)$, or $E'(J,K)$ as the case may be) and appropriate off-diagonal elements for the interaction discussed above. We have fitted more than 500 lines of the TDL spectra for each of $^{14}\text{NH}_3$ and $^{15}\text{NH}_3$ and combining this data with data from pure inversion and inversion rotation spectra have calculated accurate spectroscopic constants for both isotopic molecules. The perturbation correction to some of the energy levels in the ν_2 state of $^{14}\text{NH}_3$ and $^{15}\text{NH}_3$, arising from the off-diagonal terms in the interaction matrix are given in Table 1. It can be seen that these corrections are quite significant, especially for higher J values, and unless they are included the observed spectra could never be reproduced by theoretical calculation. Other interesting aspects of the Ammonia spectra arising

TABLE 1—PERTURBATION CORRECTION IN THE ν_2 STATE OF AMMONIA ($\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^3$)*

J	K	$^{14}\text{NH}_3$		$^{15}\text{NH}_3$	
		a	b	a	b
3	1	0	0	0	0
3	2	0	0	0	0
3	3	230	0	-22	0
5	3	-228	0	-164	0
6	8		-12	7	-13
6	4	-6 ⁷	-20	-65	-20
6	5	-4	-17	-89	-17
6	6	-1	-7	-15	-7
15	1	9 408	-25 810	9 528	47 457
15	2	49 377	14 388	-23 432	14 246
15	3	-6 207	17 190	-5 662	17 095
15	15	-656	-506	-654	-508

* These are typical ν_2 values for different J and K states. Correction for all levels of $J \leq 16$ are given in Ref. 3.

from inversion rotation interaction are discussed in more detail elsewhere^{24,25}.

Several other examples are available in literature²⁶⁻³⁰, which illustrate the application of high resolution TDL spectra in interpretation of finer interactions in molecular energy levels. Recently considerable interest has been aroused in the spectra of spherical top molecules of the type XY_6 with O_h symmetry, because of their use in laser multiphoton reaction and isotope enrichment. The spectra of spherical top molecules should be very simple in the harmonic oscillator-rigid rotator approximation because of the high degree of degeneracy of the spherical top wave function. But in reality, vibration-rotation and other interactions, remove the degeneracy, and extremely complicated energy level patterns result for such a system, giving rise to complex vibration-rotation spectra, observable by high resolution TDL spectroscopy techniques. Complete and correct interpretation of these spectra obviously will provide the confirmation of the theoretical models. Also, study of laser-induced processes in such systems require a precise knowledge of the frequencies and interactions.

In Fig. 4 we show a diode laser scan of sections of the P, Q and R branches of the ν_2 mode of SF_6 at 947 cm^{-1} . The spectra show the relatively simple structure of the low J transitions, the complex manifold structure for even moderately high J values (e.g. P-14) and the very complex band head structure of the Q-branch (see later). A complete analysis of this complicated spectrum has been done by several workers¹ and molecular parameters and interaction constants have been obtained, leading to considerable advance in the theory of spectra of spherical tops³¹⁻³³.

Diode laser spectroscopy of supersonic molecular beams: Supersonic nozzle-cooled beams are used in many molecular dynamics experiments, for spectroscopic studies of larger polyatomic molecules, production of weakly bound van der Waals molecules *etc.* Several spectroscopic techniques are available for study of such beams¹⁶ and tunable diode laser spectroscopy forms a very convenient

Fig. 4. A diode laser scan of parts of the P, Q and R branches of ν_s mode of SF_6 . Upper continuum curves are spectra of pure SF_6 expanding from a $75 \mu\text{m}$ nozzle at 300 K. Lower dashed curves represent corresponding regions of the spectra taken with a 10 cm cell at 300 K and 0.25 torr.

technique for getting information on the beam characteristics.

In a supersonic nozzle beam the gas under study (either alone, or mixed with an inert carrier gas, like He) is led into the system under high pressure (several hundreds to several thousands torr) where it is allowed to expand through a nozzle of 50-100 μm diameter into a vacuum chamber maintained at high vacuum. Under these conditions of isentropic expansion, the system cools down to very low temperatures without change of phase, attaining translational temperatures of the order of 1 K, with rotational temperatures closely following it. The vibrational temperatures are also reduced considerably, though not as low as the other two. The supercooled beam coming out of the nozzle thus provides a simple absorption spectrum, because of the depopulation of the higher rotational and vibrational levels. A study of such beam sources in itself is of great interest since the beams are in thermal non-equilibrium for many physical quantities, like translational and internal temperatures. The extremely low temperature baths of such beams also offer an ideal environment for very weak binding leading to the formation of van der Waals dimers^{37,38}, higher clusters^{39,40} and ultimately to the massive onset of condensation *etc.*^{11,13,39,41,42}. Information on all these processes can be obtained by TDL spectroscopic studies on the beam^{11-14,16,39,42}.

Typical scans for the absorption spectrum of SF_6 in the nozzle beam, are shown in Fig. 5, under various conditions of stagnation pressure and dilution. The spectra correspond to the Q-branch region of the ν_s stretching mode. The most

Fig 5. Diode laser absorption spectra of Q-branch of ν_s band of SF_6 : (A) in a 10 cm cell; (B, C and D) of nozzle-cooled SF_6 . Spectra were taken with a $75 \mu\text{m}$ nozzle under condition indicated at a distance of 7.5 mm from nozzle exit.

noticeable feature of this region is the series of sharp band heads spread over a region of only 0.25 cm^{-1} . McDowell and coworkers^{1,20,26,28,33} have shown that these band heads arise from the octahedral splitting of the triply degenerate ν_3 level, the different heads being formed from different groups, at different J values. The appearance of the heads will therefore, depend upon the rotational population distribution, their intensity thus providing a sensitive measure of the rotational temperature of the beam^{14,16}. It is clearly seen from Fig. 5 that higher stagnation pressures as well as greater dilution with an inert gas increase the cooling, leading to lower and lower rotational temperatures. Detailed information on the rotational relaxation in the beam can be obtained by just studying the diode laser spectrum under various conditions, at different points along the beam axis. Some of these results are illustrated in Fig. 6, where the rotational temperature is plotted as a function of distance on the beam axis and concentration of SF_6 in the gas stream. Analysis of the data from such studies will give parameters like fractional change in ϵ (mean random velocity per collision), γ (the average specific heat ratio), relaxation cross-section for internal degrees of freedom as a function of temperature, vibrational predissociation of van der Waals' molecules *etc.*

Fig. 6. Composite plot of rotational temperature of nozzle-cooled SF_6 , against concentration of SF_6 , and distance from nozzle exit.

Similar diode laser studies have been carried out in other systems^{41,42} also, giving information on jet profile, cluster formation, condensation *etc.* Spectral changes occurring due to condensation in the nozzle beam, in the case of ammonia, are illustrated in Fig. 7.

Application of diode laser spectroscopy in trace analysis: Tunable diode laser spectroscopy has

several advantages over conventional absorption techniques for trace and ultra trace analysis. The very high resolution available with the laser eliminates all interference from major components. Also, the peak intensity will be increased considerably compared to low resolution measurements, increasing sensitivity. The laser characteristics of high intensity and good collimation will allow the use of very long path lengths⁴³, of the order of several hundreds of meters, so that ultra trace components can be easily detected. Measurements of

Fig. 7. Diode laser absorption of $Q_{(1,1)}$ line of ν_3 band of ammonia in a nozzle beam, at a location 1 mm from nozzle exit, stagnation temp, 300 K, stagnation pressure, (a) 500, (b) 1000 and (c) 2000 torr. Onset of massive condensation is depicted by appearance of a dip at ν_0 location, corresponding to jet axis. Red and blue shifted peaks are due to Doppler shifts in flanks of expansion beam. Measured line widths are considerably larger than room temperature Doppler width of $\sim 80 \text{ MHz}$. (For further details, Ref. 42).

small quantities of absorption over large backgrounds can be easily made, and remote samples, transient species *etc.* can be studied without any difficulty. Several analytical methods have been developed using TDL techniques and we discuss one example below to illustrate the capabilities of the technique.

In the production of heavy water (D_2O) for nuclear reactors, the starting material is natural water, with deuterium concentration of about 0.015%. This deuterium is present as HDO, and analysis of the HDO concentration in the natural range is thus very useful in the early stages of enrichment. We have developed a TDL method for this analysis. The HDO line chosen, with the calibration curve is shown in Fig. 8. The total sample used in this analysis will be only about 5 mg.

Fig. 8. HDO spectrum and calibration curve. Dashed lines are N_2O lines used for calibration.

This is very important, when we consider that same method can be used for analysis of reactor grade heavy water (99.8% D_2O), where conventional infrared spectroscopy requires a few grams of the sample. More details of trace and ultra trace analyses using diode laser techniques, may be found elsewhere^{17,19,44}.

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